

USE OF EXTRACORPORAL PULSE WAVE THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH OSTEONECROSE OF THE FEMURAL HEAD CAUSED BY COVID-19

Usmonxujayeva A.A.

Adilov Sh.K.

Isomiddinov ZJ.

Adilova Z.U.

Tashkent Medical Academy
(Tashkent, Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940073>

Novel coronavirus infections caused a pandemic that began in December 2019, and on January 30, 2020, the outbreak of new coronavirus infections had been declared as a public health emergency of international concern. The new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 and the infection it causes, called COVID-19 by which, have caused the current pandemic, which has already killed more than 5 million people. [4,5]. Avascular necrosis (AVN), also called osteonecrosis, is a pathological process that involves focal bone infarction and bone death caused by injury, infection, autoimmune conditions, and chronic steroid use. According to the recent estimates of typically affecting the epiphysis of the long bones and the pelvis, the incidence of AVN to be 10–20,000 people in the United States [2]. Osteonecrosis after COVID-19 developed in a shorter period of time as compared to osteonecrosis in patients without coronavirus infection [5]. The presence of blood circulation disorders in the bone tissue which has been based on the development of the disease. Osteonecrosis of bones can occur after a coronavirus infection, even if the disease from Covid-19 is not severe. [3].

The goal. Evaluation of the effectiveness of complex physiotherapeutic methods and extracorporeal shock wave therapy in the conservative treatment of early stages of osteonecrosis of the femoral head developed after COVID-19.

Research materials and methods. Between February 2021 and January 2022, inpatients were examined who had moderate COVID-19 and were hospitalized during 2020. Patients in the III and late stages of the disease, with obvious pain syndrome and an impression fracture of the femoral head on MRI were not included in the study. The average age of the patients was $40.5, \pm 7.2$. Osteonecrosis of the femoral head is classified by Ficat i Arlet [1]. Patients were randomly divided into 3 groups (regardless of the stage of the disease). All patients underwent visual analog pain scale (VASH), WHO questionnaire, Harris test, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRT) to assess quality of life before and after treatment. In order to evaluate the effect of extracorporeal pulse wave

therapy in recommending physiotherapeutic treatment, patients were randomly divided into 2 groups.

Results. All patients had a pre-treatment score on the Harris scale above 70, which meant that the functional status of the joint was satisfactory, after treatment it had been improved by an average of 19 points. The pain scale (VASH) showed a 33% reduction in pain in the extracorporeal shock wave therapy group compared to the other group. Manual test of the hip muscles, this examination method is a method of assessing the functional condition of the muscles of the hip joint manually, that is, by hand. Tests were performed on the hip joint in flexion, writing, adduction, external and internal rotation directions. It was evaluated on a 5-point scale. It was found that the functional state of muscles improved by 28.9% in group II patients compared to group I.

Summary. It has been confirmed that the use of physiotherapeutic methods and extracorporeal pulse wave therapy in the therapeutic complex at the initial stage of the femoral head can significantly reduce the patient's probability of prosthetics, the probability of disability and return to full work. Physiotherapy methods bring significant positive changes in the lives of patients with osteonecrosis of the femoral head, which developed after the coronavirus.

list of references:

1. Gaillard F, Niknejad M, Yap J, et al. Ficat and Arlet classification of osteonecrosis of the femoral head. Reference article, Radiopaedia.org (Accessed on 30 Mar 2024) <https://doi.org/10.53347/rID-951>
2. Inneh A, Martinez K, Elizee J, et al. (August 24, 2023) COVID-19-Related Bilateral Avascular Necrosis of the Femoral Head. *Cureus* 15(8): e44034. DOI 10.7759/cureus.44034
3. Torgashin A.N., Rodionova S.S. Osteonecrosis in Patients Recovering from COVID-19: Mechanisms, Diagnosis, and Treatment at Early-Stage Disease (Review)]. *Travmatologiya i ortopediya Rossii* [Traumatology and Orthopedics of Russia]. 2022;28(1):128-137. (In Russian). <https://doi.org/10.17816/2311-2905-1707>.
4. WHO coronavirus disease (COVID-19) Dashboard. Available from: <https://data.who.int/dashboards/covid19/cases?n=c>
5. Хамидов О.А., Равшанов З.Х. Остеонекроз головки бедренной кости после COVID-19: серия случаев. *Uzbek journal of case reports*. 2022;2(1):13-17. <https://doi.org/10.55620/ujcr.2.1.2022.2>

